

Glass-Reinforced

New data on flammability resistance, weatherability, and effects of water

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TV tuner bracket is molded from glass-reinforced, flame-retardant SAN, selected for strength, rigidity, dimensional stability, and the required flame retardancy (SE-O, UL Subject 94) for the application.

THE INCREASING USE of thermoplastics in so many of today's products has brought about serious concern, from consumers as well as private and federal agencies, about the reliability and safety of these materials. Typical of such products are electrical appliances, portable tools, automotive parts, water and electrical distribution systems, and building products.

The addition of glass reinforcement, however, does much to allay these doubts. Glass not only increases thermal and mechanical performance of thermoplastics; it also improves their resistance to attack by oxidation, by extended exposure to water, by weathering, and by heat and flame.

Flammability Resistance

Among the performance requirements of thermoplastic materials, particularly for their many new areas of application, flammability resistance is getting the most attention. Generally, the approach has been to test the finished assembly. These tests, largely coordinated by Underwriters' Laboratories, duplicated the environmental conditions of the actual application.

This type of testing is time-consuming and expensive, however, and it pointed up the need for standardized test procedures. Several flammability tests have been developed and accepted that can be conducted on molded test specimens. Results can be used to predict end-use performance. The most widely accepted test methods are:

- ASTM D 635
- UL Subject 94
- IBM
- Oxygen Index

The procedures and classifications of these test methods are summarized in Table 1.

Many new applications require thermoplastic compounds classified as Self-Extinguishing (SE-1) by UL Subject 94, or equivalent. Some thermoplastics (PVC, polycarbonate, and polysulfone) have this type of flammability resistance inherently, but most (styrenics, olefins, and nylons, for example) do not. Since this latter group comprises the low cost resins, much effort has gone into making them more resistant to burning by incor-

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Table 1—Flammability Test Methods

	ASTM D 635	UL Subject 94 (Part B)*	IBM CMH 6-6436-102	Oxygen Index Method†
Test Specimen	Bar 5 x 1/2 x 1/8 in. (or 1/4 in.)	Bars 6 x 1/2 x 1/16 in. and 6 x 1/2 x 1/4 in.	Bar 5 x 1/2 x 1/8 in.	Bar 7 ± 0.15 cm long x 4.5 ± 0.5 mm wide x 3.0 ± 0.5 mm thick
Number of Specimens	10	3	5	10
Flame Characteristics	1 in. high, blue	3/4 in. high, blue	3/4 in. high, yellow-blue	6 to 12 mm long
Specimen Position	Horizontal	Vertical	Vertical	Vertical
Position of Flame to Sample	Tip of flame contacts end of specimen.	Position specimen 3/8 in. above burner tube.	Tip of flame contacts end of specimen. Burner may be tipped 20° from vertical.	Ignite top of sample.
Ignition Time	30 sec	10 sec	5, 10, 15, 20, 25, 30, 35, 40, 45, 50, 55, and 60 sec	Until entire top is burning
Ignitions per Sample	2	2	1	1
Procedure	Apply Bunsen burner flame to tip of specimen for 30 sec. If it does not ignite, wait 30 sec and apply again for 30 sec.	Apply Bunsen burner flame to lower tip of specimen for 10 sec. If it does not ignite or stops burning before the end of a 30-sec waiting period, apply again for 10 sec immediately after sample has stopped glowing.	Apply Bunsen burner flame to tip of specimen for 5 sec. If it does not ignite or stops burning before the end of a 30-sec waiting period, apply flame to specimen for 10 sec, increasing flame application time in 5-sec increments on fresh specimens up to 60 sec.	Ignite specimen so that entire top is burning. Remove flame and start timer. I. The concentration of oxygen is too high and must be reduced if: a. Specimen burns 3 min or longer, or b. Specimen burns 5 cm II. The concentration of oxygen must be raised if the specimen is extinguished before burning 3 min or 5 cm. Continue to adjust oxygen content until the limiting concentration is determined.
Classification	Burning—Sample burns more than 1 in.; the burning rate is reported in in./min. (It is common practice to omit the actual burning rate and report the result as "slow burning.") Self-extinguishing—Sample ignites but burns less than 1 in. Nonburning—Sample does not ignite.	Self-extinguishing, Group 0—Sample does not drip flaming particles which ignite the cotton and stops burning in 5 sec. 1—Sample does not drip flaming particles which ignite the cotton and stops burning within 30 sec after second flame application. 2—Sample drips flaming particles and stops burning within 30 sec after second flame application.	Class A—Materials which after a 60-sec flame-application time extinguish within 30 sec without producing flaming droplets. Class B—Materials which after 5 sec or more flame-application time extinguish within 30 sec without producing flaming droplets, but cannot withstand a 60-sec flame application. Class 0—Materials which burn for more than 30 sec or produce flaming droplets that ignite cotton after a 5-sec application.	The limiting oxygen concentration is defined as that which will meet condition I a above. At the next lower concentration, the specimen should extinguish as defined in II. Calculate oxygen index n from: $n (\%) = \frac{O_2 \times 100}{O_2 \times N_2}$ The higher the oxygen index of a material, the greater the flammability resistance.

*Part A is similar to ASTM D 635; Part B is applied only to materials not rated as "burning" by Part A.
†Penmore-Martin flammability test.

poration of flame-retardant additives.

This approach has two shortcomings: higher costs (some flame-retardant additives cost as much as \$2/lb), and reduced key physical properties. With the possible exception of flexural modulus, the physical, mechanical, and electrical properties of polymers modified with flame retardants are inferior to those of the unmodified polymers.

These limitations can be overcome by using a reinforcing glass filler in conjunction with the flame-retardant additives. Not only do glass fibers improve physical and mechanical properties; they also increase the flammability resistance of the

polymer composite, Table 2.

In polymers that are inherently flame-retardant and require no additives, impact properties are not always improved by fiber reinforcement. However, the improvements in mechanical and electrical properties and in dimensional stability of glass-fortified polymers often offset this limitation. Generally, the addition of glass fibers improves dielectric strength and dielectric constant of a polymer, but it increases the dissipation factor.

Good flexural creep strength qualifies these composites for use in load-carrying applications for periods of time. For every polymer except the

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polypropylene-based composite, the change in dimensions due to creep after 100 hr is negligible. Thus, deflection of load-carrying components can be predicted accurately, based on 100-hr apparent modulus values.

Glass-fortified, flame-retardant SAN has excellent creep resistance and is recommended for use in applications subjected to a fiber stress of 5,000 psi or less. The stronger composites (nylons, polycarbonates, and polysulfones) have superior creep resistance at higher stress levels. The creep curve for glass-fortified, flame-retardant polypropylene

did not reach a zero slope within the 1,000-hr test period, indicating that the use of this composite should be limited to applications where fiber stress does not exceed about 1,500 psi.

Preliminary thermal-degradation tests indicate that the glass-fortified, flame-retardant composites retain their properties at elevated temperatures as well as the nonflame-retardant glass-reinforced composites. Because flammability resistance and thermal endurance are of equal importance in many applications, this advantage should not be overlooked.

Table 2—Properties of Glass-Fortified, Flame-Retardant Thermoplastic Resins

Base Resin	Glass Content (%)	Flammability Rating*			Oxygen Index (%)	Yield Strength (psi)	Flexural Modulus (10 ⁶ psi)	Impact Strength, Inod (ft-lb/in.)		Heat Deflection Temp at 264 psi (F)
		ASTM D635	UL Subj 94	IRM				Notched	Unnotched	
PVC	25	NB	SE-1	A	42.0	16,000	1,200	1.1	7.8	160
Polypropylene	20	NB	SE-1	A	25.7	6,000	750	1.0	1-2	265
	0	SE	SE-1	—	—	3,400	290	0.4	2.0	230
SAN	20	NB	SE-0	—	24.0	11,500	1,100	0.8	2-3	180
	30	NB	SE-0	A	25.0	14,200	1,600	1.0	3-4	190
Modified PPO	30	SE	SE-1	B	27.8	15,700	1,200	1.5	6-7	275
	0	SE	SE-0	—	—	9,600	350	1.3	40	265
Polycarbonate	30	SE	SE-1	A	30.0	18,500	1,200	3.7	17-15	300
Polysulfone	30	SE	SE-0	A	35.0	17,500	1,200	1.3	12-13	360
	30†	SE	SE-0	A	39.5	18,000	1,200	1.8	14-15	365
	0	SE	SE-1	—	—	10,000	340	1.2	60	345
Nylon 6	30	NB	SE-0	A	25.0	22,000	1,300	1.5	15-16	405
Nylon 6/6	30	NB	SE-0	A	27.9	22,500	1,450	1.3	10-11	460
	0	NB	SE-1	—	—	10,000	360	0.9	3-4	142
Nylon 6/10	30	NB	SE-0	A	28.5	18,500	1,200	1.5	14-15	425
FEP	25	NB	SE-0	A	95.0	3,000	255	0.3	1.2	146
CTFE	15	NB	SE-0	A	83.0	5,000	400	1.2	4-5	200

*Ratings are for specific LNP Corp. compounds.

†Low smoke generation formulation.

Table 3—Effect of Weathering on Tensile Strength of UV-Stabilized Glass-Fortified Thermoplastics

Base Resin*	Initial	Tensile Strength (psi)							
		3 Months		6 Months		12 Months		24 Months	
		Phila.	L. A.	Phila.	L. A.	Phila.	L. A.	Phila.	L. A.
Polystyrene	13,400	11,700	12,350	11,950	11,600	12,750	12,100	11,900	12,400
Polycarbonate	19,470	17,200	17,500	16,830	17,600	17,370	17,270	17,300	17,000
Polyethylene	9,500	8,980	9,300	9,020	9,320	9,670	9,270	10,000	9,900
Polysulfone	14,260	13,050	13,750	13,660	13,530	13,180	13,670	13,000	13,600
Polypropylene	7,400	7,190	7,500	7,180	7,630	8,100	8,000	8,100	8,000
Nylon 6	18,000†	18,560	18,900	18,320	18,500	18,100	18,120	18,000	18,300
Nylon 6/10	20,000†	17,300	17,920	16,300	18,070	18,600	18,230	18,700	19,300
Nylon 6/6	15,000†	16,780	17,330	15,630	16,020	15,450	16,650	15,100	16,800
PVC	15,170	14,700	15,170	14,760	15,050	15,800	15,370	16,200	15,500
Thermoplastic Polyester	19,210	17,780	18,700	18,000	18,500	18,370	18,600	19,300	19,800

*All are 30% glass-fortified except PVC which contains 15% glass.

†Moisture conditioned at 50% relative humidity.

Table 4—Effect of Weathering on Impact Strength of UV-Stabilized

Base Resin*	Initial		3 Months				6 Months			
	Notched	Unnotched	Notched		Unnotched		Notched		Unnotched	
			Phila.	L. A.	Phila.	L. A.	Phila.	L. A.	Phila.	L. A.
Polystyrene	0.9	2.4	0.9	1.1	2.3	2.0	0.9	0.9	2.1	2.0
Polycarbonate	1.8	12.0	1.7	1.7	10.4	10.8	1.5	1.5	9.6	9.4
Polyethylene	1.4	6.8	1.4	1.4	5.7	5.9	1.3	1.3	5.6	5.5
Polysulfone	1.1	5.1	1.1	1.1	5.0	5.1	1.0	1.0	4.6	4.5
Polypropylene	1.1	2.4	1.0	1.1	2.9	2.6	1.1	1.1	2.8	2.5
Nylon 6	1.8	11.5	1.8	1.9	10.6	11.4	1.7	1.8	13.2	13.8
Nylon 6/10	1.8	10.6	1.7	1.6	9.1	11.0	1.7	1.5	10.3	11.3
Nylon 6/6	1.6	10.7	1.7	1.8	8.8	10.5	1.7	1.7	14.8	9.4
PVC	0.8	8.1	0.8	0.9	8.1	6.7	0.8	0.8	8.2	7.4
Thermoplastic Polyester	1.4	8.6	1.3	1.5	8.2	7.4	1.2	1.3	9.2	8.1

*All are 30% glass fortified except PVC which contains 15% glass.

Plug valve for chemical process line is made from glass-reinforced polypropylene compounded with carbon for UV protection in prolonged outdoor exposure. In addition to excellent chemical resistance of the compound, it also provides the needed impact strength and dimensional stability.

The addition of glass fibers also improves the flame-retardance of most polymers. This allows the use of less flame-retardant additives and thereby improves performance further. The glass-fiber matrix conducts heat away from the site of combustion and minimizes afterglow which is a limitation in many unreinforced flame-retardant polymers. This characteristic is especially advantageous in horizontal flame tests (ASTM D 635) where the entire bar is not surrounded by the hot gases from the burner. The strong glass-to-resin bond also adds integrity to the composite, thus minimizing dripping and decreasing the burning rate.

Weathering Resistance

Engineering thermoplastics increasingly face exposure in outdoor applications both on a short-term basis, typified by portable tool housings, and on a long-term basis, typified by water and electrical distribution systems. Like metals in such environments, these materials must resist oxidative, hydrolytically catalyzed oxidative, and chemically induced degradation. In addition, thermoplastic resins are also susceptible to thermal, bacterial,

and — most important — photochemical (UV) degradation.

The thermal and photochemical processes both result in polymer chain scission and crosslinking, although by different mechanisms. Since the photochemical process is particularly destructive under normal weather conditions, common practice is to block out ultraviolet radiation by the addition of carbon black. This produces a sharp reduction in photochemical degradation but a slight increase in thermal degradation due to black-body absorption.

Durability of glass-reinforced thermoplastics in outdoor weathering is currently under investigation in locations near Philadelphia and Los Angeles. Specimens of ten composites, representative of resin categories containing 1% carbon black, are being tested, following the specifications of ASTM D 1435. Data for intervals up to two years indicate that no appreciable decay of tensile or impact properties has occurred, Tables 3 and 4. For materials that absorb a moisture rapidly, initial values reported are for specimens conditioned at 50% RH. The initial drop in tensile strength for nylons and polycarbonate are not caused by weathering since the same drop occurs indoors at ambient conditions.

In general, no glass-fortified thermoplastic lost more than 15% of its tensile strength in the two-year period. Further, the property losses over three months are comparable to those for one year. This behavior is probably caused by initial water absorption which results in the rapid formation of a partially degraded or photo-oxidized surface. This surface is an effective light barrier which prevents further degradation.

Although the tendency is not clearly defined since the changes noted are within the range of experimental error, an increase in tensile strength occurred between three months and one year for polyethylene, polypropylene, and PVC. For instance, as shown in Table 3, 30% glass-fortified propylene had an initial tensile strength of 7,600 psi. In three months it dropped to 7,100 psi (Phila.), but at one year, the tensile strength was 8,000 psi, exceeding even the initial value. This increase may be attributable to stress relief and photochemical crosslinking.

Hydrolysis Resistance

Although much emphasis has recently been placed on the chemical resistance of polymers, little work has been done on the effects of water—the most abundant liquid in our environment. The questions that should be asked are probably overlooked since all polymers and polymer composites used in engineering applications must have good nominal resistance to water. Except in arid environments, thermoplastic components can be expected to experience continuous, long-term hydrolytic exposure.

The interaction of water—both aqueous and vapor—and polymer varies widely. No glass-reinforced thermoplastic resin simply dissolves in water. The commonly encountered modes of failure

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12 Months				24 Months			
— Notched —		— Unnotched —		— Notched —		— Unnotched —	
Phila.	L. A.	Phila.	L. A.	Phila.	L. A.	Phila.	L. A.
1.0	0.9	2.4	2.2	1.0	1.0	2.0	2.0
1.4	1.5	9.1	9.6	1.4	1.5	8.4	8.4
1.3	1.4	5.2	5.0	1.3	1.5	5.2	4.8
1.1	1.1	5.2	5.0	1.1	1.1	5.0	4.8
1.1	1.1	3.0	3.2	1.1	1.1	3.0	2.8
1.9	1.9	14.3	15.4	1.9	1.9	14.0	15.0
1.5	1.5	11.6	11.3	1.5	1.6	11.6	11.0
1.7	1.6	14.5	14.5	1.4	1.8	14.9	14.5
1.8	0.9	5.8	5.2	1.0	0.9	5.2	4.0
1.2	1.2	7.2	7.9	1.2	1.4	7.0	8.6

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Mixing valve for home water softener is molded from glass-reinforced acetal, selected because of its strength, dimensional stability, and outstanding hydrolysis resistance.

for glass-reinforced thermoplastic—swelling, stress-cracking, and wicking—like the failure of their unreinforced counterparts is apparently caused by the presence of water molecules, ionic (salt) impurities, dissolved air, and bacteria.

Water transport throughout a thermoplastic part occurs by two processes—sorption and diffusion. Sorption is the entrance of water molecules into the resin. Diffusion is the distribution by random molecular motion throughout the resin. If the water is in vapor form, the equilibrium water absorption is a function of the relative humidity. Relative humidity is a measure of partial pressure specific for water vapor. At low partial pressures, a linear relationship exists between water absorption and consequent dimensional change.

In an aqueous or high-humidity environment, the effects on a thermoplastic are more rapid. Equilibrium is controlled to a greater degree by sorption which is a function of water contact, or wetting. No thermoplastic is wet-out completely by water, however, since the surface tension of water is too high. In fact, there appears to be a correlation between hydrolytic stability (in terms of property loss) and critical surface tension of a polymer.

The 30% glass-fortified polysulfone and polypropylene have outstanding long-term resistance in 100 C water, Table 5 (polyethylene is eliminated here because of temperature, not hydrolytic

stability). The 30% glass-fortified nylon 6/10, modified PPO, and 25% PVC exhibit intermediate resistance to water at 100 C. Although glass-reinforced nylons, as expected, are the least hydrolytically stable, they have significantly greater hydrolysis resistance than the unmodified resins.

The reduction in water absorption and dimensional change values for glass-fortified nylon resins exceed those expected for a simple replacement of the resin by glass fibers. This can be explained by postulating a greater affinity of the amide groups of the nylon resin for the glass-fiber sizing systems than for water. Another peculiar feature of glass-reinforced nylon resins is the reduction in stress-cracking. In a high salt-content solution, unreinforced nylon develops cracks perpendicular to the direction of applied stress. (For example, a 50% zinc-chloride solution produces cracks in less than 45 min.) The mechanism of this stress-cracking is at present unexplained, but glass-reinforcement apparently mitigates the effect by transferring stress along the glass fibers rather than through the resin.

In highly permeable resins, a greater degree of hydrolysis takes place along the fibers, and wicking usually occurs. Under long-term exposure, 30% glass-reinforced acetal and polysulfone were hydrolyzed to such a degree that the composites had less stability than the unmodified resin.

The test method provided for both a hydrolytic and an oxidative attack. Oxygen content of the water was maintained by changing it weekly. A ranking of long-term hydrolytic aging of the series of 30% glass-fortified thermoplastic resins tested is: polypropylene > polysulfone > modified PPO > PVC > nylon 6/10 > polyacetal > SAN > polycarbonate.

Values for 24-hr water absorption at 23 C range from 0.02% for PVC to 0.25% for polyacetal; saturation values (at 23 C) range from 0.11% for modified PPO to 1.85% for nylon 6/10. Absorption values in 100 C water range from 0.40% for modified PPO to 5.41% for PVC after immersion for 5,000 hr. The reverse in ranking (short term vs long term) for PVC results not only from wetting characteristics, but also from the leaching of stabilizers and subsequent replacement with water.

Table 5—Effect of Water Aging at 100 C on Tensile Strength of Glass-Fortified Thermoplastics

Base Resin	Glass Content		Tensile Strength (psi)					
	Wt (%)	Vol (%)	0	100	1,000	5,000	10,000	50,000
SAN	30	15.4	16,700	9,500	6,000	3,000		
Polycarbonate	30	16.8	19,800	10,900	5,600	4,000		
	0	0.0	8,800	9,700	5,600	4,000		
Polysulfone	30	17.3	17,100	12,000	12,300	12,600	12,800	12,900
	0	0.0	10,500	10,900	11,900	12,500		
Polyacetal	30	19.2	14,100	10,000	6,000	2,500		
	0	0.0	9,500	9,800	9,500	2,000		
Polypropylene	30	13.2	7,600	7,900	6,600	6,200	6,000	5,500
Nylon 6/10	30	15.4	20,000	9,500	5,300	6,000	4,500	
PVC	25	15.1	17,400	11,300	5,600	6,700	5,000	
Modified PPO	30	15.2	21,500	18,000	14,000	14,000	13,500	5,000
	0	0.0	5,600	8,900	8,600	5,300	4,500	